

<https://www.abrj.org/>

Impact Factor 2.30

Research on Customer Loyalty of Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh

Author Details: Md Rezayan Hasan S Ny

School of Economics and management-Chang'an University, xian, China.

Abstract

This research endeavors to unravel the complex dynamics of customer loyalty specifically tailored to Pran Frooto Mango Juice within the dynamic market landscape of Bangladesh. In this investigation, a well-organized questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 5 for strongly agree) was utilized to collect data from consumers of Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh. The data collection process involved purposive sampling to ensure representative insights. Through the application of structural equation modeling, the study effectively identified the key factors influencing customer loyalty within the context of Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh.

The study's findings shed light on the intricate nature of customer loyalty within the context of Pran Frooto Mango Juice. The independent constructs demonstrated a moderate positive relationship among conversion cost, customer's sense of belonging connections, employee loyalty, trust & emotions, and customer satisfaction. These results underscore the pivotal role these factors play in shaping the satisfaction and loyalty of consumers in the specific market landscape of Bangladesh. Among the six factors considered, namely conversion cost, customer's sense of belonging connections, employee loyalty, and trust & emotions, four were identified as influential elements contributing significantly to the customer loyalty of Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh.

This research contributes to existing knowledge by addressing a notable research gap. While customer loyalty has been extensively explored in the literature. This study offers original insights by concentrating specifically on Pran Frooto mango Juice in the distinctive context of Bangladesh offering original perspectives that contribute not only to academic discourse but also to practical applications in the beverage industry

Keywords: Customer management, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction model, beverage products, Structural Equation Modeling, Bangladesh.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Research

The beverage sector in Bangladesh is characterized by fierce competition, involving a diverse mix of local and global players striving for market dominance. Powerhouses like Coca-Cola and PepsiCo leverage their established brands and extensive distribution networks, while local entities such as PRAN-RFL Group, featuring the popular Frooto brand, and Square Food & Beverage Limited, contribute significantly, offering a variety of beverages to cater to diverse consumer preferences. Market dynamics underscore intense competition across effervescent soft drinks, fruit juices, energy drinks, and bottled water. Innovations in product formulations, packaging, and marketing strategies drive competitiveness, with a focus on capturing the attention

of a growing consumer base. The industry faces challenges from health and wellness trends, leading to an increased demand for natural and functional beverages. The future trajectory is expected to be shaped by continuous innovations, strategic partnerships, and an unwavering commitment to meeting the evolving needs of Bangladeshi consumers.

Customer loyalty is a critical aspect of success in the competitive beverage industry, particularly in Bangladesh, where consumer preferences and brand perceptions play a significant role in shaping purchasing behavior. Within this context, Pran Frooto Mango Juice has emerged as a prominent player, offering a range of products that cater to diverse consumer needs and preferences. Understanding the factors that influence customer loyalty towards Pran Frooto Mango Juice is essential for sustaining market relevance and driving long-term success in Bangladesh's dynamic beverage industry.

Customer satisfaction emerges as a key determinant of loyalty, reflecting the extent to which Pran Frooto Mango Juice meets or exceeds customer expectations and fulfills their needs and preferences (Homburg et al., 2014). Quenched customers are more promising to exhibit loyalty, repurchase behavior, and positive word-of-mouth, contributing to the brand's long-term success and market growth (Reinartz et al., 2004). Customer satisfaction is widely recognized as a key determinant of customer loyalty (Anderson & Sullivan, 1993). Satisfied customers are more likely to exhibit repeat purchase behavior, positive spoken, and brand advocacy, thereby contributing to long-term loyalty and profitability (Reichheld, 1996). Studies have consistently demonstrated a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty across various industries, accentuating the value of delivering superior service and meeting or exceeding customer expectations (Fornell et al., 1996). Some studies said that customer loyalty is influenced by factors beyond the product itself, including the sense of belonging connections that consumers feel towards a brand. Consumers often seek brands that align with their values, beliefs, and identity, fostering a sense of community and belonging (Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001). Brands that successfully cultivate a sense of belonging among consumers can intensify customer loyalty and differentiate themselves in the marketplace (Bagozzi et al., 2002).

With a Muslim population of over 17 million, Bangladesh has rich resources, such as mosques, Halal food, and Muslim culture, which are all good reasons to attract Muslim tourists from abroad (Bangladesh National Tourism Administration, 2015). In the past ten years, there has been a notable advancement in the planning, standardization, and management of the tourism sectors, as well as in the development of infrastructure and services for both domestic and foreign travellers. In order to generate tourist dollars, an increasing number of governments are focusing heavily on the growth of international tourism, which is creating intense competition among all destinations (Zhang et al., 2000). Bangladesh is a relatively new travel destination in the global travel sector. Targeting Islamic tourists, comprehending their behavior, and meeting their needs are crucial choices if Bangladesh hopes to lead the tourism industry in the future and maintain the rising flow of foreign cash from inbound tourism. Thus, the primary goal of the study is to examine the demands and characteristics of the unexplored Muslim niche market in Bangladesh so that the tourist sector may better serve and attract this group.

Employee loyalty also plays a providential role in shaping customer loyalty by influencing the quality-of-service delivery and customer interactions. Satisfied and engaged employees are more likely to provide exceptional service, build meaningful relationships with customers, and foster loyalty and retention (Hartline et al., 2000). Thus, investing in employee satisfaction and engagement programs is essential for enhancing customer loyalty towards Pran Frooto Mango Juice. Employee loyalty and trust & emotions also play crucial roles in shaping customer loyalty towards Pran Frooto Mango Juice. Engaged and committed employees are more likely to deliver exceptional customer experiences, fostering loyalty and retention (Heskett et al., 2002). Several factors contribute to shaping customer loyalty towards Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh. One such factor is the perceived benefits gained from products, encompassing both tangible and intangible advantages that customers associate with consuming Pran Frooto Mango Juice. Research suggests that the perceived quality, taste, nutritional value, and packaging of a product significantly influence customer satisfaction and loyalty (Oliver, 2014). Studies have demonstrated that satisfied customers are more likely to exhibit repeat purchase behavior, positive word-of-mouth, and brand advocacy, thereby contributing to long-term profitability and growth (Anderson & Mittal, 2000). One of the key factors influencing customer loyalty is

the perceived benefits gained from products. Consumers often evaluate products based on their perceived value proposition, which includes factors such as taste, nutritional content, packaging, and brand reputation (Yoo & Donthu, 2001). Research suggests that consumers are more likely to exhibit loyalty towards brands that consistently deliver high-quality products and provide tangible benefits that meet their needs and preferences (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). Conversion cost, another factor explored in this study, plays a crucial role in shaping customer loyalty. Conversion cost refers to the expenses incurred by customers in the process of transitioning to and engaging with a particular product or brand. High conversion costs, such as steep prices, inconvenience, or perceived risks, can deter customers from forming loyalty towards a brand (Jacoby & Kyner, 1973). Conversely, minimizing conversion costs through competitive pricing, convenience, and perceived value can enhance customer loyalty and retention (Oliver, 1999).

In conclusion, understanding the factors influencing customer loyalty towards Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh is essential for enhancing brand performance, competitiveness, and long-term success in the beverage market. By exploring factors such as benefits gained from products, conversion cost, customer satisfaction, customer's sense of belonging connections, employee loyalty, personal reasons, trust & emotions, this study objective to provide valuable insights that can inform strategic decision-making and drive customer loyalty initiatives for Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

The focus of this study is to analyze into the issues surrounding Pran Frooto products using the lens of customer satisfaction theory. By applying this theoretical framework, the aim is to comprehensively analyze the factors influencing both positive and negative customer experiences.

Research Question

This study aims to understand what factors affect customers' loyalty of Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh. And what improvement measures can be taken to enhance the correlation between these factors and the loyalty of Frooto products.

Objective of the Study

The primary objectives of this study are to establish a comprehensive apprehension of the intricate dynamics surrounding customer loyalty towards Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh. This research activities to investigate into multifaceted aspects, aiming to achieve the following overarching goals:

- To investigate and analyze the factors surrounding Pran Frooto Mango Juice products through the lens of customer satisfaction theory.
- To identify specific factors where Pran Frooto Mango Juice products may fall short of customer expectations, exploring aspects such as Benefits Gained from Products, Conversion Cost, Customer's Sense of Belonging Connections, Employee Loyalty, Personal Reasons, Trust & Emotions.
- To provide valuable insights that can assist Pran Frooto Mango Juice in addressing and rectifying these challenges, thereby enhancing their product offerings, and fostering a more positive and satisfactory consumer experience in the competitive beverage market of Bangladesh.

Significance of the Study

In the dynamical and competitor landscape of the beverage industry, where consumer alternative evolve rapidly and market dynamics constantly shift, the significance of understanding and cultivating customer loyalty cannot be overstated. For Pran Frooto Mango Juice, a prominent and widely recognized brand in Bangladesh, deciphering the intricate determinants of customer loyalty holds immense strategic importance. Beyond being a mere academic pursuit, this research endeavor seeks to provide actionable insights that can inform strategic marketing initiatives, strengthen customer relationships, and bolster the market position of Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh's beverage industry.

The beverage industry, characterized by its diversity, innovation, and intense competition, operates within a dynamic environment shaped by changing consumer trends, technological advancements, and evolving market dynamics. Pran Frooto Mango Juice occupies a distinctive position within the beverage market of Bangladesh.

With its wide distribution network, brand recognition, and product innovation, Pran Frooto Mango Juice has entrenched itself as a household name, resonating with consumers across diverse demographic segments. However, in a market characterized by intense competition and shifting consumer preferences, maintaining and enhancing customer loyalty remains a strategic imperative for Pran Frooto Mango Juice to sustain its market leadership and drive long-term growth. By shedding light on the causal factor of customer loyalty within the context of a leading brand in Bangladesh, this study contributes to the body of knowledge surrounding consumer behavior, brand management, and marketing strategy in the beverage sector. By illuminating the determinants of customer loyalty and elucidating the pathways to sustainable growth and brand success, this research endeavor aims to empower brands to navigate the complexities of the modern marketplace, forge deeper connections with their customers, and drive long-term value and relevance in an ever-changing world.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature Review and Theoretical foundation

1. Customer Relationships Management

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) stands as a pivotal strategic approach that integrates multifaceted components including strategy, business processes, and functionalities, all aimed at establishing, upholding, and growing relationships with customers. At its core, CRM serves as a methodical framework to secure customer loyalty by diligently addressing their evolving needs and preferences. It embodies an intrinsic philosophy within organizations, guiding the creation, maintenance, sustainability, and development of the customer base, thereby shaping the trajectory of organizational success and longevity.

At its essence, CRM encapsulates a dynamic interplay of strategic initiatives and operational functionalities geared towards cultivating and nurturing enduring relationships with customers. It represents a proactive endeavor to understand, anticipate, and react to the different needs and expectations of customers across various touch points and interactions. By leveraging CRM principles and methodologies, organizations endeavor to forge meaningful connections with customers, fostering a sense of trust, loyalty, and satisfaction that transcends transactional exchanges.

a) Trust and Loyalty:

Complete customer satisfaction lays the groundwork for trust and loyalty. In cases where customers are entirely satisfied with a institution products or services, they tend to develop trust in the brand (Sanakri, K. (2023)). This trust forms the basis for two types of loyalty: trusting loyalty and snobbish loyalty Evelyn et al., (2023).

i. Trustworthy and Loyal Customers:

Customers who experience complete satisfaction not only trust the company but also develop a special affinity for specific brands. This trust leads to long-term and targeted repeat purchases. Trustworthy and loyal customers find emotional sustenance in their connection with the company, seeking a sense of belonging. They believe in the company's sincerity, its ability to satisfy their needs, and are tolerant of occasional mistakes. Even when defects arise, they provide constructive feedback without jeopardizing future purchases. These customers willingly advocate for the company, becoming enthusiastic promoters Hadi et al., (2023).

ii. Snobbish Loyalty:

In cases where customers are not entirely satisfied but find contentment in specific aspects of a company's offerings, snobbish loyalty emerges. This conditional loyalty is driven by specific benefits, such as convenience, attractive prices, prize incentives, or fear of high Conversion costs. However, snobbish loyalty is fleeting and can shift rapidly in the presence of more enticing alternatives Yanuar (2023).

2. Satisfied but Disloyal:

While customer satisfaction is crucial, it does not guarantee loyalty. Some customers, despite being satisfied, may choose to leave. For example, the U.S. automobile manufacturing industry, despite investing heavily in improving customer satisfaction, witnessed declining market share and profits. This discrepancy highlights those factors beyond satisfaction influence loyalty.

Customers may not be "unwisely loyal" unless compelled by external pressures. Dissatisfaction can arise from various factors, such as a company's environmental impact, lack of social responsibility, or inadequate handling of customer complaints Asif et al., (2023), Serhii, et al (2023).

a) Inert Loyalty:

Inert loyalty refers to customers who, despite being dissatisfied, remain with a product or service due to inertia. However, these customers can be easily swayed if competitors offer more enticing benefits.

b) Monopoly Loyalty:

Monopoly loyalty occurs in situations where customers, dissatisfied with a product or service, have no viable alternatives due to market dominance or lack of competition. In such cases, loyalty is maintained not out of satisfaction but out of a lack of alternatives.

While these forms of loyalty may temporarily benefit enterprises, they are unreliable and fragile. Unsatisfied customers, whether inert or bound by a monopoly, can be lost without warning, emphasizing the need for companies to continually strive for customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Customer Trust and Emotion

Trust Factor:

In the realm of customer purchases, where inherent risks exist, the assurance of secure transactions stands out as a primary catalyst for fostering loyalty Nugraha, Saefudin. (2022), Wayan, et al., (2022), Tanaporn, et al., (2022), Antonio, et al., (2022), Salsabila, et al., (2022). Customers, seeking to mitigate risks during the purchasing process, are inclined to cultivate long-term relationships with businesses they trust implicitly. Research underscores that trust forms the bedrock of customer loyalty, simplifying repeat purchases and instilling a sense of dependence on the company. In a market often characterized by a lack of trust—akin to "swimming with sharks"—companies solely fixated on immediate profits and neglectful of customer sentiments are unlikely to secure customer favor. Conversely, companies that earn customer trust are poised not only to achieve satisfaction but also to cultivate unwavering loyalty.

According to Gul (2014), client trust is characterized as the content held by a consumer that a company or service provider will fulfill their needs. When a consumer trusts a company, they exhibit a strong belief in the quality of the company's products and services. In the service industry context, Levy and Hino (2016) assert that trust is closely linked to customers' expectations and their belief that assist providers will fulfill their promises. This belief implies a commitment to reducing the costs associated with negotiate agreements (Sahin, Zehir, & Kitapci, 2012).

In his study, Gul (2014) operationalized customer trustingness using the following indicators: 1) the product instills a sense of safety in consumers, and 2) the products and services offered by the company are guaranteed to be of high quality. Similarly, Levy and Hino (2016) suggest that customer trust can be assessed based on indicators such as: 1) the product's reliability, and 2) the product's fulfillment of its obligations to consumers. According to Levy and Hino (2016), trust is significantly influenced by customer satisfaction and also plays a pivotal role in fostering consumer loyalty.

In essence, customer trust answer as the foundation upon which prospering customer relationships are improved. It reflects the level of assurance that consumers have in a company's quality to deliver on its commitment and consistently meet their expectations. As customers perceive a company to be trustworthy and reliable, they are more likely to acquire a sense of loyalty and commitment to the brand. Therefore, fostering trust among customers is essential for enhancing brand reputation, promoting repeat business, and cultivating long-term customer relationships in today's competitive marketplace.

Emotional Factors:

In contemporary consumer behavior, the influence of feeling on customer loyalty has become increasingly pronounced. While companies may offer similar benefits, it is the emotional connection that distinguishes a brand. Deep emotional communication becomes the linchpin for constructing customer loyalty that transcends mere transactional relationships. When emotional integration occurs between a company and its customers, the

association evolves from a simple exchange to a deeply intertwined partnership (Philipp, et al., (2023). Customers with profound connections to a company exhibit resilience to temptation and are less prone to betray the relationship Omer, et al., (2023). Notably, the preference for a brand can transcend rational factors like quality and price. The sentiments towards a company, as highlighted by experts like Kawada of Landor Associate and Vicky Lenz, become a defining factor in consumer choices.

According to Vicky Lenz's "Emotional Marketing," emotion emerges as a crucial market asset, constituting the true foundation of sales, customer loyalty, and profitability. Canadian marketing professor Jim Banos draws parallels between customer relationships and interpersonal connections, emphasizing elements like trust, community sense, common goals, respect, and dependence. Establishing an emotional connection, rooted in a genuine understanding of customer perspectives and a commitment to customer care, becomes the linchpin for winning the hearts and unwavering loyalty of customers. In essence, the bedrock of lasting customer allegiance lies not only in economic transactions but in the establishment of emotional bonds that resonate with the customer's values and aspirations.

The service environment plays a pivotal role in shaping client emotions, both ethically and physically (DeCelles, DeVoe, Rafaeli, & Agasi, 2019; Liang, Lin, & Liang, 2011). Within the service industry context, providers often exhibit affirmatory emotions, such as a friendly attitude and a warm smile, which have a direct impact on enhancing affirmatory emotions in customers. Moreover, customer behavior is intricately linked to ethically activities that involve direct interaction with products or service providers. Customers form certain evaluate and make judgments based on these interactions, which subsequently influence their levels of contentment or dissatisfaction with the service received (Burns & Neisner, 2006).

As a result, an increase in consumer satisfaction tends to elevate an one-on-one inclination to revisit the store or service provider. The positive emotions evoked by a welcoming service environment and courteous interactions contribute significantly to fostering a sense of satisfaction among customers. This satisfaction, in turn, reinforces loyalty and encourages repeat patronage, thereby enhancing the overall customer experience and bolstering the reputation of the service provider in the eyes of consumers. Thus, the service environment serves as a crucial determinant of customer perceptions and emotions, exerting a profound influence on their satisfaction levels and subsequent behavioral intentions.

Benefits gain from the product

Companies can offer loyalty rewards to encourage customer loyalty and prevent the risk of losing existing patrons and discouraging new ones from becoming longstanding customers. The provision of incentives, such as discounts and special favors, plays a pivotal role in influencing customers to establish enduring relationships with enterprises and derive benefits from loyalty. It is essential for companies to prioritize the needs of their existing clientele and not solely focus on attracting new customers with superior conditions. Mistreating old customers can result in a substantial loss of loyalty (Laith, A., et al., (2010), Gabriel, et al., (2018).

Discounts and special favors serve as compelling incentives for customized to forge long-term connections with companies. It is evident that the driving force behind customer loyalty lies in the tangible benefits they can accrue. If loyal customers do not receive more advantages than new customers, their loyalty becomes constrained, leading to the risk of losing existing patrons and discouraging new ones from becoming longstanding customers. Hence, the question arises: Can companies offer loyalty rewards?

The provision of incentives plays a pivotal role in influencing whether customers choose to remain loyal. Unfortunately, some companies adopt the counterproductive approach of consistently offering superior conditions to new customers while neglecting the needs of their existing clientele. This approach inadvertently encourages regression rather than progression, posing a significant setback to customer loyalty. Just as old clothes may not be as flashy as new ones, and old acquaintances may not hold the initial charm of new ones, mistreating old customized can effect in a substantial loss of fidelity.

Conversion Cost

Conversion costs in the realm of customer loyalty encompass the challenges and expenses customers face when considering a shift from one enterprise to another. These costs include time, energy, economic factors, and emotional considerations. Time and energy conversion costs involve learning curves, temporal investments, and effort [Daniel et al., (2023)]. Economic conversion costs involve the loss of interests and monetary investments [Jeffrey, Wu. (2023)]. Emotional conversion costs encompass the loss of personal and brand relationships [Michael, D. et al., (2022)].

According to Jeffrey, Wu (2023), conversion costs, which include the loss of tangible resources, personal connections, and emotional investments, present a challenge for competitors in fostering customer loyalty. However, simply raising conversion costs without nurturing corporate image and product/service quality can lead to customer betrayal and detachment in the long run [Niloofar, A. et al., (2022)].

Customers' sense of belonging connections

It is considered a fundamental human need, encompassing various social contexts such as family, neighborhood, social class, friendships, and work relationships (Maslow, 1954). Belongingness not only influences psychological well-being but also encompasses an individual's evaluation of their surrounding environment. The sense of belonging is shaped by how individuals perceive their alignment (or misalignment) with their surroundings (Master, 2016). When individuals feel that they do not fit into their environment, there is a perceived mismatch between the individual and their surroundings (Hagerty & Patusky, 1995). Conversely, when individuals experience a sense of belonging, they feel valued, accepted, and appreciated (Hagerty, 1992). Sense of belonging is often examined in relation to the concept of community, which primarily pertains to the sense of belonging within neighborhood contexts (Magan, 2021).

Employees' Loyalty

Satisfied and loyal employees are more likely to excel in providing high-quality products and services, contributing to customer satisfaction. This positive synergy extends to customers' evaluation of the company, shaping their perception and influencing their loyalty. Therefore, fostering a positive and loyal employee environment is strategically important for overall organizational success [Eman, et al., (2023), Zulher., et al., (2023), and Hoang, et al., (2023)].

According to Allen and Grisaffe (2001), loyalty represents a psychological state that characterizes an employee's relationship with the organization they work for, influencing their determination to remain with the organization. Mathieu and Zajac (1990) define loyalty as an attachment to the organization, often manifested as an emotional response, especially when employees strongly believe in organizational goals and values and desire to maintain their membership within the organization. Becker et al. (1995) describe loyalty as a strong desire to remain a member of an organization, a willingness to exert high levels of effort for the organization's sake, and a definite belief in and acceptance of the organization's values and goals.

While job contentment represents an efficacious response to specific job features and an attitude toward a job, employee loyalty is a broader response encompassing the entire organization (Chen, 2006). Employer job satisfaction exerts a positive impact on the organizational loyalty of employees (Fletcher and Williams, 1996). Martensen and Gronholdt (2001) suggest that employee satisfaction is positively associated with employees' loyalty to their companies. Similarly, studies by Al-Aameri (2000) and Fang (2001) systematically report a strong relationship between organizational loyalty of employees and employee job satisfaction (Wu and Norman, 2006).

Definition of all Factors

Conversion Cost: Conversion cost refers to the expenses incurred in persuading or convincing a customer to switch from one product or brand to another. It includes various marketing and promotional costs aimed at winning over consumers.

Trust and Emotion: Trust and emotion involve the feelings of reliability, confidence, and connection that a customer develops toward a brand or product. Building trust and evoking positive emotions are crucial for establishing a lasting relationship with customers.

Benefits Gained from Products: Benefits gained from products are the advantages, positive outcomes, or value that customers derive from using a particular product. These benefits can include practical features, emotional satisfaction, or any improvement in the customer's life.

Customer Loyalty: Customer loyalty is the degree of faithfulness or commitment a customer has towards a specific brand or product. It is often reflected in repeated purchases and a reluctance to switch to competing brands.

Personal Reasons: Personal reasons refer to individual motivations or factors that determinant a customer's decision-making process. These reasons can vary widely and may include personal preferences, habits, or specific needs.

Customer's Sense of Belonging Connections: The customer's awareness of belonging connections relates to the emotional attachment and feeling of being part of a community or group associated with a particular brand. It reflects the customer's identification with the brand beyond just a transactional relationship.

Employee Loyalty: Employee loyalty pertains to the commitment dedication of employees to a particular company or organization. It involves a strong allegiance to the employer, leading to increased productivity, longevity of service, and positive representation of the company.

Conceptual Framework

This exploratory study examines the relationships among several key constructs, including Benefits gained from products, trust & Emotions, conversion cost, personal reasons, employee loyalty, customers sense of belonging connection as independent constructs, customer satisfaction as a dependent construct, The conceptual model, depicted in Figure 1, visually represents these interrelationships among the constructs under investigation. The conceptual framework serves as a roadmap for exploring and analyzing the intricate relationships between these key factors and their collective impact on customer satisfaction.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework, Source: Researcher's own contribution [From Literature Review]

RESEARCH ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY ISSUES OF PRAN FROOTO MANGO JUICE

Company Background

PRAN-RFL Group grew from a small commercial company founded by General (Ret) Amjad Khan Chowdhury in 1981 to a huge conglomerate. It has had a considerable impact on Bangladesh's economic landscape by operating in a variety of areas such as agro, plastics, and real estate. The group's well-known

brand, "PRAN," is well-known in Bangladesh and over 106 other countries. PRAN-RFL Group began in the food processing industry in 1997 and expanded its range to include plastic manufacture in 2005. The corporation has achieved noteworthy global success with over 200 food products, including juices, drinks, and snacks that adhere to international quality standards. Despite challenges from a competing brand in 2008, the debut of Frooto, a mango-flavored product, was a success. The company's objective is to create jobs and promote socioeconomic development. Pran Frooto Mango Juice is headquartered in Dhaka and operates strategically, with distribution locations assuring widespread availability. The financial summary shows constant development, with sales expected to reach Tk. 3.15 billion in 2022. Market competitiveness, changing consumer tastes, and supply chain complexities are all challenges. Customers' main concerns are product availability and packaging preferences. Solutions include competitive analysis, customer trend adaptation, and supply chain simplification. Innovative solutions are used to solve key issues such as market competition, consumer preferences, supply chain complexities, economic dynamics, regulatory compliance, and environmental sustainability. Financial difficulties originate from operational costs and market uncertainty, which necessitate constant modification. Finally, Pran Frooto Mango Juice overcomes obstacles by strategic initiatives that prioritize consumer satisfaction, sustainability, and financial resiliency.

Product Portfolio

Pran Frooto's product portfolio reflects a fusion of traditional flavors and modern convenience. The company is best known for its extensive range of fruit juices, with the flagship product being the Frooto Mango Juice. Pran Frooto has successfully blended global trends with local preferences, introducing a variety of flavors that cater to the diverse palate of the Bangladeshi consumer.

Market Presence and Reach

Pran Frooto's impact on the Bangladeshi market is substantial, with its products becoming household staples across the nation. The brand's market presence extends beyond urban centers, reaching rural communities and fostering a sense of unity through shared experiences.

Problem solving idea

The idea of applying customer relationship management theory for problem analysis is to conduct specific research and analysis using customer loyalty theory.

Factor-1 (Benefits Gained from Products): This factor includes four variables like overall well-being enhancement, contribution to daily fruit intake, convenience as a nutrition source, and good value for price. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Benefits Gained from Products" factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Factor-2 (Conversion Cost): This factor includes four variables like reasonable price and good value, cost-effective choice, affordability through discounts and promotions, perception of a good deal. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Conversion Cost" factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Factor-3 (Customer Satisfaction): This factor includes three variables like consistency in living up to reputation, influence of return rate on satisfaction, and consideration of budget in purchasing. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Customer Satisfaction" factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Factor-4 (Customer's Sense of Belonging Connections): This factor includes three variables like trust in catering to needs and preferences, strong connection with other customers, and perception of listening to customer feedback. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Customer's

Sense of Belonging Connections " factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Factor-5 (Employee Loyalty): This factor includes three variables like dedication and commitment of employees, belief in motivated and satisfied employees, and employees' strong sense of belonging and loyalty. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Employee Loyalty" factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Factor-6 (Personal Reasons): This factor includes three variables like loyalty influenced by brand's quality and consistency, trust in Pran Frooto mango juice as a reliable brand, and influence of friend's and family's preferences. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Personal Reasons" factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Factor-7 (Trust & Emotions): This factor includes five variables like trust in quality and safety, consistent meeting of expectations, feeling satisfied and content, pleasant and enjoyable experience, and confidence in brand's commitment to high-quality products. These pivotal variables collectively contribute to shaping and defining the "Trust & Emotions" factor, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse advantages that consumers attribute to their experience with Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Hypotheses

Customer satisfaction has emerged as a pivotal determinant in the success and sustainability of businesses across various industries. It encapsulates the subjective evaluation of a customer's experiences with a production or service and reflects their overall contentment with their interactions with the organization. Understanding the factors that influence customer satisfaction has become imperative for businesses seeking to enhance their competitive edge and foster long-term customer relationships. Conversion cost, another factor under scrutiny, refers to the expenses incurred by customers during the conversion process, such as transaction fees, shipping charges, or installation costs. Despite being a potential barrier to purchase, the way customers perceive and evaluate conversion costs can influence their overall satisfaction with the transaction. Employee loyalty, both perceived by customers and exhibited by the organization's workforce, contributes significantly to the overall customer experience.

Trust and emotions represent fundamental pillars of customer satisfaction, influencing perceptions of reliability, credibility, and emotional resonance with the brand or organization. Customers who trust the organization and perceive emotional connections in their interactions are more likely to experience heightened satisfaction and loyalty. Finally, understanding the intricate interplay between these factors—ranging from tangible benefits and costs to emotional connections and personal motivations—is essential for businesses striving to cultivate enduring relationships with their customers and enhance overall satisfaction levels.

H₁: There is significant positive relation between Benefits Gained from Products and Customer Satisfaction

H₂: There is significant positive relation between Conversion Cost and Customer Satisfaction

H₃: There is significant positive relation between Customer's Sense of Belonging Connections and Customer Satisfaction

H₄: There is significant positive relation between Employee Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction

H₅: There is significant positive relation between Personal Reasons and Customer Satisfaction

H₆: There is significant positive relation between Trust & Emotions and Customer Satisfaction

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY, DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS DISCUSSION

Statistical Analysis

This chapter presents the statistical analyses passageway in examining the impact of all independent factors, namely benefits gained from products, conversion cost, customer's sense of belonging connections, employee loyalty, personal reasons, and trust & emotions, exerted a significantly positive influence on customer

satisfaction (CS) for Bangladeshi Pran Frooto Mango Juice Company Limited. In the quest to unravel the influential factors shaping customer satisfaction, this study adopts a multifaceted approach, harnessing the power of both factor analysis and structural equation modeling (SEM) to delve deep into the underlying dynamics. The utilization of SmartPLS software emerges as a strategic choice, driven by its unparalleled capability to navigate complex relationships and facilitate a rigorous analysis of the data. This process of dimension reduction not only enhances the interpretability of the data but also facilitates a heavy understanding of the factors influencing customer satisfaction.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) emerges as a cornerstone of the analytical framework, offering a comprehensive approach to model complex causal relationships among latent variables. These latent constructs may encompass diverse aspects such as product quality, service reliability, pricing, convenience, and brand reputation, each acting a unique role in shaping customer satisfaction. Moreover, SEM facilitates a comprehensive examination of the causal pathways linking these latent constructs, allowing researchers to test theoretical hypotheses and evaluate the relative importance of each factor in driving overall satisfaction. By specifying a structural model that captures the direct and indirect effects of various predictors on customer satisfaction, SEM enables researchers to assess the overall fit of the framework to the empirical data and identify potential areas for refinement or further investigation.

In tandem with the use of advanced statistical method, the survey adopts a judgment sampling technique to collect data from the target population. Judgment sampling, a non-probability sampling method, involves the intended selection of individuals or cases based on the researcher's judgment and expertise. While judgment sampling may lack the randomization inherent in probability sampling methods, it offers several advantages in terms of efficiency, feasibility, and accessibility, particularly in studies where the target population is difficult to define or access. This targeted approach enables researchers to gather insights from key stakeholders, experts, or practitioners who possess valuable knowledge and expertise relevant to the study's objectives.

Demographic Information

The survey centered on individuals who had consumed Pran Frooto Mango Juice in Bangladesh, aiming to garner insights into their demographic profiles and consumption habits. Analyzing the data presented in Table 1, a notable gender disparity among respondents is apparent, with over 77% identifying as male and approximately 23% as female. This gender skew reflects prevailing consumption patterns or preferences within the sample population and underscores the value of understanding gender dynamics in the circumstance of consumer behavior and market segmentation strategies.

Delving deeper into the age distribution among respondents reveals intriguing patterns and trends. The data indicate that a substantial proportion, approximately 42%, falls within the age bracket of 24-29 years, signifying a significant demographic segment with a propensity for consuming Pran Frooto Mango Juice. Furthermore, more than 35% of respondents belong to the 18-23 years age group, indicating a sizable cohort of younger consumers who are actively engaged with the brand. Interestingly, a smaller yet noteworthy segment of respondents, comprising nearly 6%, falls into the age category of 36 years and above. This demographic segment represents an older cohort of consumers whose consumption habits and preferences may differ from their younger counterparts, thus warranting distinct marketing strategies and tailored product offerings to cater to their unique needs and preferences. The responses reveal a diverse spectrum of consumption behaviors among participants, with over 42% indicating rare consumption of Pran Frooto Mango products.

Moreover, these findings serve as a foundational basis for informing strategical marketing initiatives, product development endeavors, and targeted promotional campaigns aimed at resonating with diverse consumer segments and enhancing brand loyalty.

Table 1: Demographic information of respondents based on the questionnaire

Variable's Name	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	135	77.1
	Female	60	22.9
Age	18-23 years	60	31
	24-29 years	81	42
	30-35 years	39	20
	36 years and above	15	7
	Daily	22	11
How often do you consume Pran Frooto Mango products?	Weekly	39	20
	Monthly	34	17
	Rarely	82	42
	Never	18	10

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

Conclusions

Trust & Emotions:

The findings underscore the critical importance of trust and emotional connections in nurturing and sustaining customer loyalty. Trust serves as the foundation upon which abiding relationships between brands and customers are built. It encompasses the belief and confidence that customers have in a brand's ability to deliver on its promises, uphold its commitments, and consistently provide value and quality. When customers trust a brand, they feel confident in their decision to engage with the brand and are more likely to remain loyal over time. Trust fosters a sense of security, reliability, and dependability, which are essential elements in cultivating lasting relationships with customers.

For Pran Frooto Mango Juice, enhancing trust and emotional connections requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses various aspects of the customer experience. Firstly, the brand must prioritize transparency and honesty in its interactions with customers. Additionally, Pran Frooto Mango Juice should focus on delivering consistent and reliable experiences across all touchpoints. Consistency builds trust by demonstrating reliability and dependability, which are key drivers of customer loyalty. Whether through product quality, customer service, or marketing communications, Pran Frooto Mango Juice must ensure that every interaction with customers reflects the brand's values and commitment to excellence.

So, trust and emotional connections are fundamental drivers of customer loyalty for Pran Frooto Mango Juice. By prioritizing transparency, consistency, personalization, and storytelling, Pran Frooto Mango Juice can strengthen trust and emotional connections with its customers, fostering long-term loyalty and advocacy.

Conversion Cost:

Conversion costs refer to the expenses, both monetary and non-monetary, incurred by customers when transitioning to and engaging with a particular product or brand. These costs encompass various factors, consider the price of the product, the time and effort expended in the decision-making process, and any perceived risks associated with the purchase. Understanding and effectively managing conversion costs are essential for businesses seeking to foster customer loyalty and drive repeat purchases. Strategic pricing strategies play a pivotal role in mitigating conversion costs and enhancing customer loyalty. Pricing strategies such as penetration pricing, promotional pricing, and value-based pricing can effectively attract customers by providing them with perceived value and affordability.

Customer's Sense of Belonging Connections:

Customers' awareness of belonging and connection with a brand represents a profound and multifaceted aspect of consumer behavior, deeply intertwined with loyalty and brand preference. In the context of Pran

Frooto Mango Juice, understanding and nurturing this sense of belonging among consumers can significantly impact their attachment to the brand and their propensity for repeat purchases. Research consistently demonstrates that consumers who feel a strong awareness of belonging and connection with a brand are more likely to exhibit greater loyalty and advocacy behaviors.

One of the primary mechanisms through which brands can foster a awareness of belonging among consumers is by creating inclusive and engaging brand experiences. This involves going beyond traditional marketing tactics to build meaningful connections with consumers through storytelling, community-building initiatives, and experiential activations. Moreover, leveraging digital platforms and social media channels can be instrumental in nurturing a sense of belonging among consumers.

Employee Loyalty:

The correlation between employee loyalty and customer loyalty represents a critical aspect of organizational success, underscoring the interconnectedness between employee satisfaction and customer outcomes. Research consistently demonstrates that a committed and satisfied workforce plays a crucial role in driving positive customer experiences and fostering long-term loyalty. As such, organizations across industries, including those in the beverage sector like Pran Frooto Mango Juice, must prioritize employee satisfaction and engagement initiatives to cultivate a workforce that is invested in delivering exceptional service and value to customers. Investing in employee satisfaction and engagement programs is imperative for organizations seeking to enhance customer loyalty.

Recommendations

Strengthen Trust-Building Initiatives:

Implement strategies to enhance trust, such as transparent communication, consistent product quality, and responsive customer service. Building an emotional connection with customers through marketing campaigns that evoke positive emotions can further reinforce trust.

Optimize Conversion Costs:

Conduct a thorough analysis of pricing strategies and promotional activities. Implement cost-effective measures to reduce conversion costs, ensuring that customers perceive the value proposition of Pran Frooto Mango Juice.

Cultivate a Sense of Belonging:

Develop marketing campaigns that foster a sense of community and belonging among customers. Utilize social media and other platforms to create spaces for customers to share their experiences and feel connected to the brand.

Invest in Employee Satisfaction:

Prioritize employee satisfaction through training, development programs, and recognition initiatives. Satisfied and engaged employees are more likely to deliver exceptional customer experiences, positively influencing customer loyalty.

Continuous Monitoring and Adaptation:

Regularly assess customer feedback, market dynamics, and employee satisfaction levels. Adapt strategies based on changing customer preferences and market trends to maintain a competitive edge and sustain customer loyalty over time.

REFERENCES

- i. Aaker, D. A., & Joachimsthaler, E. (1999). The Lure of Global Brands. *Harvard Business Review*, 77(6), 137-144.
- ii. Abigail, R., Hanlon. (2023). Belonging. 65-C4N§§§§. doi: 10.1093/oso/9780190648107.003.0004
- iii. Akter, S., D'ambra, J., & Ray, P. (2011). An evaluation of PLS-based complex models: the roles of power analysis, predictive relevance, and GoF index.
- iv. Al-Aameri, A. S. (2000). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment for nurses. *Saudi medical journal*, 21(6), 531-535.
- v. Allen, N. J., & Grisaffe, D. B. (2001). Employee commitment to the organization and customer reactions: Mapping the linkages. *Human Resource Management Review*, 11(3), 209-236.
- vi. Aprianif, A., Oktavia, O., Saptono, A., Riyadi, R., & Diananda, A. (2023). THE CORRELATION BETWEEN THE SENSE OF BELONGING AND LEARNING MOTIVATION TOWARD THE STUDENT'S SOCIAL WELFARE. *International Journal of Business, Law, and Education*, 4(2), 402-410.
- vii. Bagozzi, R. P., & Yi, Y. (1988). On the Evaluation of Structural Equation Models. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 16(1), 74-94.
- viii. Becker, T. E., Randall, D. M., & Riegel, C. D. (1995). The multidimensional view of commitment and the theory of reasoned action: A comparative evaluation. *Journal of Management*, 21(4), 617-638.
- ix. Bibb, S. and Kourdi, J. (2007). *A Question of Trust*. London: Marshall Cavendish.
- x. Blumberg, B., Cooper, D.R. and Schindler, P.S. (2011), *Business Research Methods* (11th ed.). McGraw Hill, New York, NY, USA.
- xi. Burns, D. J., & Neisner, L. (2006). Customer satisfaction in a retail setting: The contribution of emotion. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 34(1), 49–66. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09590550610642819>
- xii. Cardoso, A., Gabriel, M., Figueiredo, J., Oliveira, I., Rêgo, R., Silva, R., ... & Meirinhos, G. (2022). Trust and loyalty in building the brand relationship with the customer: empirical analysis in a retail chain in northern Brazil. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(3), 109.
- xiii. Chaudhuri, A. and Holbrook, M.B. (2001). The chain of effects from brand trust and brand affect to brand performance: The role of brand loyalty. *Journal of Marketing*, 65(1), 81-93
- xiv. Chen, C. F. (2006). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and flight attendants' turnover intentions: A note. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 12(5), 274-276.
- xv. Chin, W. W. (2010). How to Write Up and Report PLS Analyses. *Handbook of Partial Least Squares*, 655-690.
- xvi. Cho, S., Woods, R. H., Jang, S. S., & Erdem, M. (2006). Measuring the impact of human resource management practices on hospitality firms' performances. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 25(2), 262-277.
- xvii. COHEN, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum
- xviii. Cohen, J. (2013). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. Routledge.
- xix. Cook, R. D. (1979). Influential observations in linear regression. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 74(365), 169-174.
- xx. Daniel, Reynolds. (2023). Conversion. *Renaissance and Reformation*, doi: 10.1093/obo/9780195399301-0498
- xxi. DeCelles, K. A., DeVoe, S. E., Rafaeli, A., & Agasi, S. (2019). Helping to reduce fights before flights: How environmental stressors in organizations shape customer emotions and customer–employee interactions. *Personnel Psychology*, 72(1), 49-80.

- xxii. Denison, D.R. (1990). Corporate culture and organizational effectiveness. Ann Arbor, MI: Aviat, Inc.
- xxiii. Dewayani, A., Widayanti, S., & Fitriana, N. H. I. (2023). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) PT Bhineka Rahsa Nusantara dalam Perspektif Kepuasan Pelanggan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi*, 23(1), 266-275.
- xxiv. Doaei, H., Rezaei, A., & Khajei, R. (2011). The impact of relationship marketing tactics on customer loyalty: the mediation role of relationship quality. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 2(3), 83.
- xxv. Eman, Mohamed, Abd-El-Salam. (2023). Exploring factors affecting Employee Loyalty through the relationship between Service Quality and Management Commitment a case study analysis in the iron and steel industry Al Ezz Dekheila Steel Company in Egypt. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(2) doi: 10.1080/23311975.2023.2212492
- xxvi. Evelyn, Wijaya., Achmad, Tavip, Junaedi., Stefani, Chandra., S., Suyono. (2023). Trust, satisfaction, and loyalty of islamic bank customers: role of religiosity. *Jurnal aplikasi manajemen*, doi: 10.21776/ub.jam.2023.021.02.17
- xxvii. Fang, Y. (2001). Turnover propensity and its causes among Singapore nurses: an empirical study. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12(5), 859-871.
- xxviii. Fisher, C.D. (2000), "Mood and emotions while working: missing pieces of job satisfaction?", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 21, 185-202.
- xxix. Fletcher, C. and Williams, R. (1996), "Performance management, job satisfaction and organizational commitment", *British Journal of Management*, 7(2), 169-79.
- xxx. Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 382-388.
- xxxi. Gabriel, Sperandio, Milan., Luiz, Antonio, Slongo., Luciene, Eberle., Deonir, De, Toni., Suélen, Bebber. (2018). Determinants of customer loyalty: a study with customers of a Brazilian bank. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 25(9):3935-3950. doi: 10.1108/BIJ-08-2017-0231
- xxxii. George, D. (2011). SPSS for windows step by step: A simple study guide and reference, 17.0 update, 10/e. Pearson Education India.
- xxxiii. Good, C., Rattan, A., & Dweck, C. S. (2012). Why do women opt out? Sense of belonging and women's representation in mathematics. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 102(4), 700-717.
- xxxiv. Guiffrida, D. (2005). Othermothering as a framework for understanding African American students' definitions of student-centered faculty. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 76(6), 701-23
- xxxv. Gul, R. (2014). The relationship between reputation, customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 4(3), 2161-7104.
- xxxvi. Hadi Kurniadi and Junaid Ali Saeed Rana (2023). The power of trust: How does consumer trust impact satisfaction and loyalty in Indonesian digital business? *Innovative Marketing*, 19(2), 236-249. doi:10.21511/im.19(2).2023.19
- xxxvii. Hagerty, B. M., Lynch-Sauer, J., Patusky, K. L., Bouwsema, M., & Collier, P. (1992). Sense of belonging: A vital mental health concept. *Archives of psychiatric nursing*, 6(3), 172-177.
- xxxviii. Hagerty, B. M., Patusky, K. (1995). Developing a measure of sense of belonging.
- xxxix. Hair Jr., J.F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C.M., Gudergan, S.P., 2017. *Advanced Issues in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling*. Sage Publications.
- xl. Hair, J. F. J., Anderson, R. E., Tatham, R. L., Black, W. C. (1998). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (5th Edition). Prentice Hall: Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, USA.
- xli. Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., and Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*, 2nd Ed., Sage: Thousand Oaks.

- xlii. Halimi, A. B., Chavosh, A., & Choshalyc, S. H. (2011). The influence of relationship marketing tactics on customer's loyalty in B2C relationship—the role of communication and personalization. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science*, (31), 49-56.
- xliii. Henseler, J. (2017). Partial least squares path modeling. *Advanced methods for modeling markets*, 361-381.
- xliv. Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. *Advances in international marketing*, 20, 277-319.
- xlv. Henseler, J., Ringle, C.M., Sarstedt, M., 2015. A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *J. Acad. Market. Sci.* 43 (1), 115-135.
- xlvi. Hoang, Trinh., Dao, Thi, Hong, Van., The, Kien, Nguyen. (2023). What determines employees' job satisfaction and loyalty? Evidence from Vietnamese enterprises. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 10(2):67-76. doi: 10.21833/ijaas.2023.02.009
- xlvii. Hsu, S.H. (2008). Developing an index for online customer satisfaction: adaptation of American Customer Satisfaction Index. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 34(4), 3033-3042
- xlviii. Hu, L. T., & Bentler, P. M. (1998). Fit indices in covariance structure modeling: Sensitivity to under parameterized model misspecification. *Psychological methods*, 3(4), 424-453.
- xlix. Hulland, J. (1999). Use of partial least squares (PLS) in strategic management research: A review of four recent studies. *Strategic Management Journal*, 20(2), 195-204.
- l. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, Rand McNally, Chicago, IL, pp. 1297-349.